

THE TYPES AND USAGE OF COLLOCATIONS (ON THE BASIS OF EXAMPLES TAKEN FROM “WINDMILLS OF THE GODS” BY SYDNEY SHELDON)

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***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada ingliz tilidagi kollokatsiyalar, ularning turlari va qo'llanish sferalari haqida atoqli olimlarning fikrlari o'rganib chiqilgan va ilmiy ishimizning asosiy material bo'lmish amerikalik taniqli yozuvchi Sidni Sheldon qalamiga mansub “Windmills of the gods” asaridan bir qancha kollokatsiyalar tahlil qilingan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** frazeologik birliklar, kollokatsiya, kollokator, asos, idioma, erkin birikmalar, yarim frazemalar, jumla, lug'at, mazmun, izoh, so'z birikmasi.*

***Annotation.** The article explores English collocations, their types, and spheres of usage, based on the views of prominent scholars in the field. A number of collocations from the novel Windmills of the Gods by the renowned American writer Sidney Sheldon, which serves as the primary material for our research, have been analyzed in detail.*

***Keywords:** phraseological units, collocation, collocator, base, idiom, free combinations, semi-phraseemes, sentence, vocabulary, meaning, explanation, word combination.*

***Аннотация.** В статье рассматриваются английские коллокации, их виды и сферы употребления на основе мнений выдающихся учёных. Проведен подробный анализ ряда коллокаций из произведения Windmills of the Gods («Мельницы богов») знаменитого американского писателя Сидни Шелдона, которое является основным материалом нашего исследования.*

***Ключевые слова:** фразеологические единицы, коллокация, коллокатор, база, идиома, свободные сочетания, полужразеологизмы, предложение, лексика, значение, пояснение, словосочетание.*

To understand which combinations are a subset of collocational patterns and therefore qualify as collocations, we need to define what collocations are. Although Mel'cuk rightly points out that there is “no universally accepted formal definition of collocations nor a proposal for their uniform and systematic treatment in dictionaries” (Mel'cuk 1998:23), most scholars do agree on two points.

First, it is generally accepted that collocations consist of two parts: **a collocator** and **a base** (Hausmann 2004) using the term binemes as contrasted with monemes).

Second, it is usually agreed that these two elements show a degree of binding / fixation or restriction to each other, thus forming a unit that fits somewhere in between idioms and free combinations. In this respect, some authors use the terms ‘semi-phraseemes’ (Mel'cuk 1998:30) or ‘encoding idioms’ (Croft & Cruse 2004:250), implying that collocations, like idioms and phraseemes, behave as units. As it is this latter feature in particular –the degree of binding / fixation / unification – that remains vague and problematic, we intend to focus on it in some detail, starting from the following working definition. A collocation is – a word group consisting

of two conceptual elements: a **collocator** (determinants) and a **base** (determinatum) – of a certain syntactic type (Noun + Noun, Verb + Noun, Adjective + Noun, Adverb + Verb, Adverb + Adjective) – showing a semantic, type-based, relationship between the two elements – the more the collocator is, conceptually speaking, type-bound (bound to a conceptual type or category) and the more it is, lexically speaking, token-bound (bound to a lexical token/item), the more we are dealing with a collocation that conceptually and lexically forms a unit, i.e. one that is a lexical collocation.

In the following we intend to comment on each part of the definition separately.

– A collocation is a word group consisting of two conceptual elements: a **collocator** (determinans) and a **base** (determinatum)

By this it is meant that a collocation is the combination of two concepts or frames which, as a rule, are in a dependency relation, one (the collocator or modifier) modifying the other (the base or head). So, for instance, *in commit suicide* we will consider *suicide* to be the base or topic triggering the frame. This means that there is a dominant frame, evoked by *suicide* and a dependent one (commit) zooming in on a specific aspect of the dominant frame (Some authors, such as Poulsen 2005, prefer to speak of an ‘interdependent’ relationship, even if there is a bias towards / dominance of one of the elements.). Defining collocations as the combination of two concepts or frames distinguishes them from idioms, which, although showing a compositional structure, contain only one conceptor frame (pay attention, however, that collocations can be recursively defined so that one collocation can be embedded in another and thus lead to more than just two elements, as is the case in (*take measures = take strong measures*)).

– of a certain syntactic type (Noun + Noun, Verb + Noun, Adjective + Noun, Adverb + Verb, Adverb + Adjective)

Some scholars divide collocations into two groups taking into considerations of their usage sphere: Lexical collocations and grammatical collocations:

(Lexical) collocations are usage-determined or preferred syntagmatic relations between two lexemes in a specific syntactic pattern. Both lexemes make an isolable semantic contribution to the word combination but they do not have the same status. Semantically autonomous, the ‘base’ of a collocation is selected first by a language user for its independent meaning. The second element, i.e. the ‘collocate’ or ‘**collocator**’, is selected by and semantically dependent on the ‘base’. Examples: *heavy rain, closely linked, apologize profusely*.

Grammatical collocations are restricted combinations of a lexical and a grammatical word, typically **verb / noun / adjective + preposition**, e.g. *depend on, cope with, a contribution to, afraid of, angry at, interested in*. The term ‘grammatical collocation’ is borrowed from Benson et al. (1986) but our definition is slightly more restricted as these authors also use the term to refer to other valency patterns, e.g. **avoid+ -ing** form, which we do not consider to be part of the phraseological spectrum.

A collocation may be defined as a combination of words which can be observed in close proximity to each other in discourse. John Rupert Firth (1957: 179), to whom the notion is attributed, called a collocation “the company it [a word] keeps”. Examples include *strong tea* (*heavy tea), *to have patience* (*to keep patience), or *a close look* (*an exact look). Open collocations are usual combinations of constituents used in their literal meanings and freely substitutable (Howarth 1998: 28). Restricted collocations have one constituent that is used in a specialized or figurative sense. Phraseology researchers have often considered only a specific type of collocation – so-called restricted collocations – as part of the phrasicon. There are at least two reasons, however, why free (or open) collocations are also worth mentioning here. The first

reason is their relevance for the foreign language learner. Whereas learners have to understand PUs only passively when they occur in a text, that is, as a receptive language skill, collocations may constitute a serious problem for language production, as they must be mastered as an active language skill. The learner of English has to become familiar with subtleties like the fact that in English the verbs *gain*, *gather* or *acquire* are collocates of the base *experience* and that *make* cannot be used. As reference books, the student has recourse to collocation dictionaries (e.g. the Student’s Dictionary of Collocations 1989 by Morton Benson / Evelyn Benson / Robert Ilson). In addition, in our modern era of huge electronic corpora, a web concordancer provides further collocation-learning help. The second reason why collocations deserve our special attention is their role in texts. Humorous modifications and puns do not only draw on PUs and restricted collocations, but also on open collocations, as the joke in and the headline in show.

Customer: Waiter! What’s wrong with these eggs?

Waiter: Don’t ask me, sir. I only **laid the table**.

Pay attention to the collocation continuum by Howarth (1998: 28)

	Free combinations	Restricted collocations	Figurative idioms	Pure idioms
Lexical composites: (verb + noun)	<i>blow a trumpet</i>	<i>blow a fuse</i>	<i>blow your own trumpet</i>	<i>blow the gaff</i>
Grammatical composites: (preposition + noun)	<i>under the table</i>	<i>under attack</i>	<i>under the microscope</i>	<i>under the weather</i>

Whereas free collocations allow a free substitution of words and are understood in their literal senses, in restricted collocations one constituent (usually the collocate) is used in a transferred (figurative) meaning. Figurative idioms, as Howarth points out, have metaphorical meanings alongside a current literal interpretation. Pure idioms are the most opaque ones since their meaning cannot be derived from the meanings of the constituents.

This part of the definition implies that:

a. the combinations we are dealing with are called lexical in the sense that they combine lexical items; combinations of a lexical item and a function word (preposition, conjunction etc.) are not taken into account here and will be regarded as grammatical collocations.

b. The order in which the elements are given reflects a semantic dependency relationship, not a syntactical one: the left member is dependent on the right one. In other words, the right member is considered to be the **base** (being the independent or dominant frame), the left member the **collocator** (the dependent frame).

c. The dominant item here is the one that most strongly evokes the frame. Which item is independent (dominant) and which is not is often a matter of dispute (Poulsen 2005:271). In discussing, we intend to take a functional point of view: in a combination in which a noun and a verb occur, it is the noun, as a rule, that triggers the frame functioning as the topic, while the verb fulfils the role of comment (In this respect it should be noted that the more concrete the meaning of the verb, the easier it is to consider it the topic of the discourse. Compare for instance *take* in *take measures* (where *take* is an abstract support verb) with *take the car* (*take* = *make*

use of) and *take a book* (*take = grasp*). In the last case (*take a book*) it can be argued that *take* triggers the frame and *book* is one of the many fillers of the slot / class of ‘*graspable objects*’).

– showing a semantic, type-based, relationship between the two elements

In a frame-based approach the combinatorial possibilities of lexical units (LUs) to form constructions such as compounds and collocations are defined by the conceptual structure of the component LUs. In other words, given two LUs, X and Y, each with their own conceptual frame, X and Y will only combine and unify if the modifying dependent LU fits the slot of the modified dominant LU, thus specifying, among other things, the meaning of the latter. In this respect there is no fundamental difference in combinatorial behavior between collocations and (a substantial subset of) compounds, although their function may differ, collocations having a more characterizing and compounds a more categorizing function (for example, Feilke 2004 who states (Feilke 2004:54) collocations rather characterize while compounds rather categorize).

– the more the collocator is, conceptually speaking, type-bound (bound to a conceptual type or category) and the more it is, lexically speaking, token-bound (bound to a lexical token/item), the more we are dealing with a collocation that conceptually and lexically forms a unit, i.e. a lexical collocation.

Although most definitions of collocations mention a degree of binding as a characteristic feature, they usually remain rather vague in their elaboration of this phenomenon. In fact, the more collocational a collocation is, the more its collocator is, conceptually speaking, type-bound and, lexically speaking, token-bound. This can only be understood fully against the background of frames with their slot-filler format. In a concrete combination such as *drink coffee*, for instance, *drink* acts as a filler for the slot ‘WAY OF CONSUMING’, a slot that is typical for the type DRINK. In other words, for the meaning of the word *coffee*, it is very relevant, just as it is for other drinks, that we drink it. On the other hand, the word *drink* is not bound to the word *coffee* in an exclusive way. As a matter of fact, *drink* is a default value for all drinks and so it is more type-than token bound. As a consequence, although there is a binding between the elements of drink coffee, this binding is less strong than that between weak and coffee. This could suggest that lexical combinatorics are subject to (type-bound) rules and exceptions. However, linguistic reality is less straightforward. Besides rules and exceptions, the productivity / generality of rules also plays a role, as do preferences and prototypicality.

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